

IT AUDIT AS A SERVICE: IMPACT ON UNCOVERING TECHNOLOGY AND INFORMATION SECURITY RISKS

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ABSTRACT

In today's dynamic business environment, the convergence of IT audit with risk management, governance, and cybersecurity is paramount. This paper explores the concept of IT Audit as a Service (ITaaS), emphasizing its strategic importance in addressing proactive measures to mitigate risks and enhance decision-making processes. By recognizing cyber risk as an intrinsic business risk, ITaaS provides a comprehensive approach to maintaining organizational resilience. Through continuous control assessments and effectiveness measurements, ITaaS supports organizations in strengthening their governance frameworks and ensuring robust cybersecurity postures. Traditionally, Internal Audit (IA) has acted as the third line of defense, providing independent and objective assurance. However, ITaaS can go beyond this role by offering a fresh eyes perspective, enabling more dynamic and forward-looking insights. This study underscores the pivotal role of ITaaS in fostering a proactive, resilient, and well-governed enterprise landscape.

Keywords: Compliance, Cybersecurity, IT Audit, Software, Software Development Lifecycle (SDLC)

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1. INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this paper is to explore the concept of IT Audit as a Service (ITaaS) and its significant impact on uncovering technology and information security risks. IT audits may serve various objectives and multiple parties within an organization, and therefore there may be different definitions of IT audit quality. These definitions may include ideas such as impact or effectiveness, completeness as related to different standards, and efficiency or cost. One purpose of IT audits is to provide management with assurance that a system or automated process is meeting its objectives. Specifically, the focus may be on managements' control responsibilities over computer-based information assets and processes [1].

ITaaS delves into the unknown, bringing out perspectives that establish new processes and improve existing systems to ensure they are secure and compliant. It can be a mix of regulatory obligations and internal priorities. By leveraging specialized expertise and advanced tools, ITaaS provides comprehensive assessments of IT systems, ensuring robust security and compliance. This service model enhances the identification of vulnerabilities and inefficiencies, enabling organizations to proactively address potential threats. The result is a fortified IT infrastructure that supports business continuity and resilience against cyber threats.

ITaaS acts as an independent body that objectively assesses organizational risks and enhances the overall security posture, safeguarding against regulatory, reputational, and financial loss, it can be a third-party provider or an internally developed team. The fundamental objective of conducting an audit is to evaluate and ensure the accuracy, compliance, and efficiency of an organization's business and operational processes. ITaaS is revolutionizing the traditional approach to audits by offering a more dynamic and comprehensive method for identifying and mitigating risks. ITaaS is governed by standards set by the Institute of Internal Auditors (IIA), that ensures alignment with industry regulatory requirements. The IIA is the internal audit profession's leader in standards, certification, education, research, and technical guidance throughout the world. Generally, members work in internal auditing, risk management, governance, internal control, information technology audit, education, and security [2].

In the following sections, we will explore the structure of IT Audit in depth, use of data analytics, real-world use cases, ITaaS benefits and challenges, thereby providing a comprehensive understanding of how this innovative approach is transforming the field of IT auditing.

2. OVERVIEW OF IT AUDIT PROCESSES

IT Audit process comprises of five key phases: pre-planning, planning, fieldwork, reporting, and process improvements.

A deep dive into the internal audit process reveals a structured approach consisting of several key steps:

- **Pre-Planning:** This initial phase involves understanding the organization's environment, its processes, and identifying the key areas of focus for the audit. Pre-planning also includes gathering relevant documents, setting the scope and objectives of the audit, and determining the resources required.
- **Planning:** During the planning phase, auditors develop a detailed audit plan, which includes defining the audit criteria, objectives, and methodology. This phase also involves conducting risk assessments to prioritize areas with the highest risk and impact on the organization.

- **Fieldwork:** The fieldwork phase is where the actual auditing takes place. Auditors collect and analyze data, perform tests, and evaluate controls to determine if they are operating effectively. This phase requires a thorough examination of records, interviews with personnel, and observation of processes.
- **Reporting:** After completing the fieldwork, auditors compile their findings into a comprehensive report. This report outlines any issues identified, assesses their impact on the organization, and provides recommendations for improvement. The report is presented to management and other relevant stakeholders for review and action.
- **Process Improvements or Continuous Improvements:** The final phase focuses on implementing the recommendations provided in the audit report. This may involve revising policies, enhancing controls, or adopting new procedures to address the identified issues. Continuous improvement is an ongoing process, ensuring that the organization adapts to changes and maintains a robust control environment.

The above-described audit processes are run by an audit team that comprises of:

- **Chief Audit Executive (CAE):** The top executive responsible for overseeing the internal audit function. Ensures alignment with organizational goals and regulatory requirements.
- **Senior Director of IT Audit:** Leads the IT audit division, sets strategic direction, and ensures the execution of the audit plan. Reports to the CAE.
- **Directors of IT Audit:** Oversee specific areas or regions within the IT audit function. Ensure that audits are conducted in accordance with professional standards and organizational policies.
- **Managers of IT Audit:** Manage day-to-day audit activities, including planning, executing, and reporting on audits. Supervise audit staff and ensure the quality of audit work.
- **Senior IT Auditors:** Conduct detailed audits and reviews of IT systems and processes. Provide insights and recommendations for improvement. May mentor junior staff.
- **IT Audit Associates:** Assist in conducting audits, including data collection and analysis. Work under the supervision of senior auditors and managers
- **Data Analytics Team:** Supports the audit process by providing advanced data analysis and insights. This team helps identify patterns, anomalies, and potential risks within the organization's data, enhancing the audit's effectiveness and efficiency.

3. USE CASES

The use cases presented will demonstrate how Internal Audit as a Service (ITaaS) can add value by enhancing processes and uncovering deficiencies. Below are two high-level examples outlining the audit objectives and illustrating how ITaaS can provide independent opinions and assurance, ultimately driving improvements and strengthening organizational resilience.

3.1. Use Case #1: Using IT Audit as a Service (ITaaS) for Disaster Recovery Audits

Disaster recovery is an organization's method of regaining access and functionality to its IT infrastructure after events like a natural disaster, cyber attack, or even business disruptions related to the COVID-19 pandemic. A variety of disaster recovery (DR) methods can be part of a disaster recovery plan. DR is one aspect of business continuity [3].

For any potential risk to a company, engaging IT Audit as a Service (ITaaS) provides an independent and objective opinion on the effectiveness of disaster recovery plans. ITaaS can be utilized to determine if the following key aspects of a disaster recovery program are in place and functioning effectively:

- Business Impact Analysis (BIA)
 - a) Objective: Ensure that a BIA exists and is periodically refreshed.
 - b) Audit Focus: Assess whether the BIA accurately identifies critical business processes and technologies, both internal and external dependencies, and includes appropriate tier ratings for Recovery Time Objectives (RTOs) and Recovery Point Objectives (RPOs).
- Disaster Recovery Plans (DRPs)
 - a) Objective: Verify that DRPs are adequately documented, approved, and include essential elements.
 - b) Audit Focus: Evaluate whether the DRPs cover key elements such as plan activation, roles and responsibilities, communication processes, and recovery procedures, ensuring they are comprehensive and effective.
- Governance Processes
 - a) Objective: Establish and implement governance processes over the disaster recovery program.
 - b) Audit Focus: Ensure that risks are timely and adequately remediated, and that issues are appropriately escalated, prioritized, and reported. Assess the effectiveness of governance structures in overseeing the disaster recovery program.
- Testing and Updating DRPs
 - a) Objective: Ensure DRPs are tested periodically and updated as necessary.
 - b) Audit Focus: Determine if the DRPs are tested regularly, identify gaps during testing, and verify that these gaps are properly addressed in the updated plans. Ensure updated plans are distributed timely to guarantee the continuation of critical business processes and systems.
- Regulatory Compliance
 - a) Objective: Verify that regulatory requirements are adequately addressed and reported.
 - b) Audit Focus: Assess the processes in place to ensure compliance with relevant laws and regulations. In addition, ensure that these processes are robust and effective in maintaining regulatory adherence.

By leveraging ITaaS for disaster recovery audits, organizations can ensure that their DR plans are comprehensive, up-to-date, and effective in minimizing the impact of disasters on their operations. This proactive approach helps maintain business continuity, protect data, and comply with regulatory requirements, ultimately enhancing the organization's resilience against potential threats.

3.2. Use Case #2: Streamlining the Software Development Lifecycle (SDLC)

The Software Development Lifecycle (SDLC) is the cost-effective and time-efficient process that development teams use to design and build high-quality software. The goal of SDLC is to minimize project risks through forward planning so that software meets customer expectations during production and beyond [4].

The SDLC consists of several phases: planning, design and development, and deployment and maintenance. Each phase is essential to ensure the delivery of reliable, secure, and high-performing software. IT Audit as a Service (ITaaS) can be leveraged to provide an objective evaluation of the SDLC, ensuring that all phases—from planning to deployment and maintenance are executed efficiently and effectively. This use case demonstrates how ITaaS can enhance the SDLC process, ensuring robust compliance, security, and operational efficiency.

3.2.1. Engaging ITaaS for SDLC Audit

- Planning Phase:
 1. Objective: Ensure that all appropriate stakeholders are engaged, approvals are obtained, and committee oversight is in place.
 2. Audit Focus: Confirm that planning activities involve the right stakeholders, that there is clear communication and documentation of project goals, and that necessary approvals have been secured. Assess whether committee oversight mechanisms are effective in guiding the project.
- Design and Development Phase:
 1. Objective: Verify that requirements are clearly defined to meet the intended use of software products and confirm adherence to company-approved tools and methodologies.
 2. Audit Focus: a) Assess whether requirements were gathered accurately and are well-documented. b) Evaluate if Agile methodologies were used to obtain continuous feedback, ensuring that coding standards prescribed by company policies were followed. c) Check for the separation of duties in coding and testing to maintain integrity and security and confirm that code is stored in company-approved repositories.
- Deployment and Maintenance Phase:
 1. Objective: Confirm that software was released according to internal protocols and with the necessary approvals.
 2. Audit Focus: a) Evaluate the release process to ensure it follows internal protocols and that all necessary approvals were obtained. b) Check if communication about the release was sent to the appropriate stakeholders. c) Assess if monitoring mechanisms are in place, and d) verify that incoming issues are triaged according to internal policies and that alerts are set up to notify relevant teams of any issues.

Engaging ITaaS for auditing the SDLC ensures a comprehensive, independent evaluation of the software development process. By focusing on critical areas such as planning, design and development, and deployment and maintenance, ITaaS helps organizations enhance the efficiency, security, and compliance of their software projects. This proactive approach not only ensures the delivery of high-quality software but also contributes to a robust and compliant IT infrastructure, supporting overall business objectives.

4. BENEFITS

- Strengthens Internal Technology Controls:
 1. Technology internal audits assess your internal controls related to IT systems, actions, and processes. This includes evaluating whether controls are effectively designed, implemented, and functioning as intended, regardless of personnel changes. By ensuring that technology controls are robust, audits help maintain operational integrity and security.
 2. Example: A technology internal audit might evaluate an organization's access control systems to ensure that only authorized personnel can access sensitive data. The audit would check whether the role-based access controls are correctly implemented and enforced, regardless of changes in the IT team or staff. For instance, the audit might discover that access permissions for former employees were not properly revoked, leading to potential security risks.
- Efficiency:
 1. Technology internal audits identify inefficiencies and redundancies in your IT processes and governance practices. By uncovering overlapping or outdated practices, auditors provide recommendations to streamline technology operations, optimize resource use, and enhance overall efficiency, leading to time and cost savings.
 2. Example: An internal audit could reveal inefficiencies in the IT infrastructure, such as redundant data backups being performed on multiple systems or overlapping software applications used across departments. The audit might recommend consolidating backup solutions and standardizing software tools to reduce costs and streamline IT operations, ultimately saving time and resources.
- Security:
 1. Internal audits of technology systems scrutinize your cybersecurity posture by identifying and evaluating digital assets and their security measures. These audits detect vulnerabilities in your IT infrastructure and network, offering advice on strengthening defenses and closing security gaps to protect against cyber threats.
 2. Example: During a technology audit, auditors might assess the organization's network security to identify vulnerabilities such as outdated firewalls or unpatched software. For instance, they might discover that a critical server has not been updated with the latest security patches, making it susceptible to cyber-attacks. The audit would provide recommendations to address these vulnerabilities and strengthen overall network security.
- Integrity:
 1. Audits ensure the integrity of technology processes and systems by verifying that they function as intended and as promised by management. They assess whether IT systems operate reliably and consistently, identifying potential risks such as software malfunctions or operational failures that could impact performance.
 2. Example: An audit could focus on a company's transaction processing system to ensure it operates as intended without errors.

For instance, the audit might identify a flaw in the system that causes occasional data discrepancies during high-transaction periods, leading to incorrect financial reports. The audit would verify that the system performs reliably and recommend fixes to prevent such errors.

- **Reduced Risk:**
 1. Technology internal audits evaluate the risks associated with your IT environment and assess the effectiveness of your risk mitigation strategies. By highlighting areas where risk management measures may be lacking, audits provide actionable insights and recommendations to address these gaps and reduce overall risk exposure.
 2. Example: A technology internal audit might assess the risk management practices related to data encryption. If the audit finds that encryption protocols are not consistently applied across all data storage solutions, it will highlight this as a significant risk. The audit would provide guidance on implementing uniform encryption standards to mitigate the risk of data breaches and enhance overall security.
- **Improved Compliance:**
 1. Internal technology audits review your adherence to relevant laws, regulations, and industry standards applicable to your IT systems. They assess whether your technology practices comply with these requirements and provide guidance on corrective actions needed to achieve and maintain compliance, thereby avoiding potential legal and regulatory issues.
 2. Example: An internal audit might review a company's adherence to data protection regulations like GDPR. The audit could uncover that certain data handling practices do not fully comply with regulatory requirements, such as insufficient consent mechanisms for data collection. The audit would recommend changes to ensure compliance with GDPR, such as implementing stronger consent processes and updating privacy policies.

5. CHALLENGES FOR IT AUDITS AS A SERVICE (ITAAS)

Despite the opportunities offered by digital transformation, IT Audits as a Service (ITaaS) face several significant challenges:

- **Rapid Technological Change:** The swift evolution of technology necessitates that IT auditors continually update their skills and knowledge to stay ahead of emerging threats and vulnerabilities. One such challenge is the rapid pace of technological change, which requires IT auditors to continuously update their skills and knowledge to keep pace with emerging threats and vulnerabilities [5].
- **Complexity of Digital Systems:** The intricate nature of modern digital systems and processes complicates comprehensive assessments and risk identification.
- **Cybersecurity Risks:** As organizations increasingly rely on digital technologies, they become more susceptible to cyber threats such as data breaches and ransomware attacks. IT auditors must, therefore, remain vigilant in assessing cybersecurity controls and ensuring the resilience of digital infrastructure [5].
- **Regulatory Compliance:** Navigating a complex landscape of data protection and privacy regulations poses significant challenges. IT auditors must stay current with evolving regulatory requirements and ensure organizational compliance with relevant laws and standards [5].

Overall, ITaaS must effectively address these challenges to help organizations leverage digital technologies while managing associated risks.

6. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, IT Audits as a Service (ITaaS) are pivotal in navigating the complexities of modern technology environments. By incorporating data analytics, automation, and integrated audit approaches, ITaaS not only enhances the efficiency and effectiveness of audit processes but also provides a more comprehensive view of an organization's technology landscape. ITaaS strive to foster a holistic view of an organization's IT environment, aligning various audit functions and ensuring that technology, compliance, and operational assessments are cohesively addressed. The help in addressing operational excellence by strengthening governance process and enhance overall security by conforming best security practices are incorporated. Additionally, they provide an added assurance that business processes are adhered to relevant laws, regulations, and industry standards, avoiding potential legal and financial penalties. As organizations continue to adopt and integrate new technologies, leveraging ITaaS with these modern methodologies will be crucial in maintaining robust security, compliance, and operational resilience.

REFERENCES

- [1] Stael, Dale, Douglas Havelka, and Jeffrey W. Merhout. "An analysis of attributes that impact information technology audit quality: A study of IT and financial audit practitioners." *International Journal of Accounting Information Systems* 13.1 (2012): 60-79.
- [2] The Institute of Internal Auditors. About the IIA. <https://www.theiia.org/en/about-us/>
- [3] VMware. Disaster Recovery. <https://www.vmware.com/topics/disaster-recovery>
- [4] Amazon. What is SDLC. <https://aws.amazon.com/what-is/sdlc/>
- [5] Azizi, M., Hakimi, M., Amiri, F., & Shahidzay, A. K. (2024). The Role of IT (Information Technology) Audit in Digital Transformation: Opportunities and Challenges. *Open Access Indonesia Journal of Social Sciences*, 7(2), 1473-1482.
- [6] Gartner, Inc. (2023). Magic Quadrant for CRM Customer Engagement Center. <https://www.gartner.com/en/doc/444047>

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